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INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO FOR RESTORING THE ANATOMICAL INTEGRITY OF THE RETINA AFTER ITS DETACHMENT

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Retinal detachment (RD) is a pathological condition that leads to vision loss without timely surgical treatment. We conducted a study [1] to determine the safest method of treating retinal detachments and to improve the medical tools for restoring the anatomical integrity and repositioning of the detached retina, provided that a reliable chorioretinal adhesion is obtained and the number of side effects of surgical intervention is minimized [2].

Patients with significant RD undergo one of three retreatment procedures: Pneumatic Retinopexy, Scleral Buckling, and/or Pars Plana Vitrectomy. Techniques and tools for these procedures have been developed, but the methods themselves still have a significant number of complications. A possible alternative to their further improvement may be a fundamentally new method of treatment, coagulation of the retina with high-frequency electric current (HFEC), for which significant improvement of the tool is still possible. Technical achievements in conducting operations to eliminate RD using existing microsurgical instruments were analyzed. Proprietary method and a tool developed for it were proposed.

To fulfill the conditions for improving the method, a chorioretinal high-frequency electrocoagulation operation with suprachoroidal access, a modified EK-300M1 generator (Kyiv, Ukraine) with an electrode with a gold hemispherical tip of 25 gauge and electrical generation parameters of 66 kHz, 10–16 V, 0.1 A was proposed, which causes chorioretinal adhesion in the place where the electrode is used. The method of calculating the parameters of heat transfer from the electrocoagulation tool to the tissues and fluids of the eye was selected. Destructive phenomena in the retina from the thermal effect of tissue coagulation in the form of the destruction of rods, cones, the development of cysts, the loss of bipolar, amacrine, horizontal and ganglion cells were noted. Atrophic changes in the retina were minimal at a voltage of 10–12 V.

Each of the retinopexy methods has its own disadvantages: cryopexy leads to the formation of intracellular ice crystals, diffuse atrophy of the retinal pigment epithelium and damage to small vessels, a decrease in the layer of photoreceptor cells and the formation of chorioretinal adhesions [3]. When using a laser, its light energy is mainly absorbed by the cells of the pigment epithelium and transmitted to the neighboring tissues. Overheating leads to the destruction of photoreceptors, choriocapillaries, the formation of scars that fix the retina too firmly [4]. The photosensory layer also thins, and ganglion cells are strongly irritated, strong adhesion does not occur in the first days, but only on the fourth day, and gains strength in only three weeks. At the same time, the effect does not depend on the type of the laser. Cryocoagulation and photocoagulation with an argon laser destroy the hematoretinal barrier, which can be the cause of proliferative vitreoretinopathy. In addition, the risk of recurrence of RD when using laser and cryoretinopexy reaches approximately 10% [5], mainly due to insufficient retinopexy, proliferative vitreoretinopathy or a new retinal rupture.

The problem of improving the methods of restoring the anatomical position of the retinal layers has been relevant for many decades, but it does not lead to a significant reduction in the number of complications. The proposed method and tool

for its application causes the creation of a reliable chorioretinal adhesion in a short period of time after surgical intervention with minimal thermal tissue damage. The use of the method of chorioretinal high-frequency electrocoagulation with suprachoroidal access is recommended in conditions of urgent restoration of vision, but not recommended for the prevention of retinal detachment in retinopathies. The proposed operative method and the tool improved for this purpose correspond to modern Ukrainian clinical protocols for the treatment of retinal detachment.

References:

1. Saoud O, Serhiienko A. Selection and improvement of the method and tool for restoring the anatomical integrity of the retina after its detachment. *Inter Collegas*. 2022;9(2):9p. In press. <https://doi.org/10.35339/ic.9.2.sas>
2. Saoud O, Sergiienko A, Korol A, Umanets M, Petrovski G, Rehak M, Lytvynchuk L. Morphological changes of eye tissues after the influence of high-frequency electric current welding with suprachoroidal approach to induce chorioretinal adhesion. Proceedings of the 23rd Congress of European Association for Vision and Eye Research (EVER), 13–15 Oct 2022, Valencia, Spain. Poster No.762. S.150. Pr. p. 97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7339553>
3. Curtin VT, Fujino T, Norton EW. Comparative histopathology of cryosurgery and photocoagulation. Observations on the advantages of cryosurgery in retinal detachment operations. *Arch Ophthalmol*. 1966;75(5):674-82. DOI: 10.1001/archopht.1966.00970050676018. PMID: 5936373.
4. Tso MO, Wallow IH, Elgin S. Experimental photocoagulation of the human retina. I. Correlation of physical, clinical, and pathologic data. *Arch Ophthalmol*. 1977;95(6):1035-40. DOI: 10.1001/archopht.1977.04450060121012. PMID: 869746.
5. Bentivoglio M, Valmaggia C, Scholl HPN, Guber J. Comparative study of endolaser versus cryocoagulation in vitrectomy for rhegmatogenous retinal detachment. *BMC Ophthalmol*. 2019;19(1):96. DOI: 10.1186/s12886-019-1099-9. PMID: 31023285.

CONTENTS

Balynska O., Blahuta R. Pros and cons of distance learning (on the example of higher education institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine).....	3
Batiuk O. Improving critical infrastructure cybersecurity: international experience.....	8
Baula O. Investment and innovation component of the country's international competitiveness in the conditions of technoglobalism.....	13
Bielkina-Kovalchuk O. School mediation as a mean of forming a safe educational environment.....	18
Bogdanovska N.V., Kalonova I.V., Boichenko C.Y. Correction of myofascial dysfunction of athletes in the conditions of their training activity.....	23
Bogdanovskiy I, Konokh A. Theoretical and methodical planting the formation of the pedagogical approach in the physical education of preschool children.....	28
Chabanenko M. Artificial intelligence and new media journalism.....	32
Chupaylenko O., Kozlov A. Methodological approaches to personnel management in the customs case.....	37
Fisunenکو N. Modern development of business processes: impact of digitalization on economic development.....	42
Herevenko A. Modern possibilities of developing educational and methodological support.....	45
Ivanovska O., Merkur'ev A. Theoretical-methodical basics of developing physical therapy programs for non-specific lower back pain.....	49
Ivanska O. The use of psychological aspects in the system of rehabilitation of children during the martial law in Ukraine.....	56
Ivasyshyna N. Prospects for the development of the quality of services.....	61

Mykhalchuk R. Holocaust oral history sources in the educational and scientific discourse (based on the sources of the Shoah Foundation of the University of Southern California and Yahad-In Unum in France).....	118
Nesterenko V., Ohniev V. Methodological aspects of the assessment of the need for palliative and hospice care in Ukraine.....	122
Кузнiченко О., Iльченко М. Деякi питання реформування юридичної освiти в Украiнi.....	125
Овчаренко Т., Лебеденко М. Штучний iнтелект в сучасному мистецтвi.....	130
Петрук В. Впровадження iнновацiйних пiдходiв у процесi соцiального захисту молодiї сiм'ї.....	135
Полiщук Л. Пушкар Т. Перекладацькi трансформацiї та iх рiзноманiття у перекладних виданнях художньої лiтератури.....	146
Разумова Г. Оскома О. Маркетингова полiтика розподiлу суб'єктiв господарювання.....	151
<u>Saoud O., Serhiienko A. Innovative approach to for restoring the anatomical integrity of the retina after its detachment.....</u>	<u>155</u>
Савченко Л., Ткачук Н., Котлярова М. Особливостi формування професiйно-педагогiчної культури сучасного педагога.....	158
Савченко В., Кононенко Л. Розвиток аграрного сектору Украiни як соцiально-економiчної системи..	164
Щербакова Н. Планування туристичної привабливостi дестинацiй	168
Шемуда М., Бондаренко Р. Вiйськова лексика як особливий елемент лексичної системи англiйської мови	172
Штангей С. Наочнiсть графiчних засобiв для дiтей з iнтелектуальними порушеннями розвитку.....	176
Smutchak Z. Impact of forced migration from Ukraine on the economy of the European union.....	180

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